

DEFINITE-CCRI

Report on project appraisal proceedings

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Executive Summary

This document describes the investor project appraisal process and execution, carried out by the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium, which involved a comprehensive review of projects by potential investors and technical partners. The process evaluated the readiness of projects for financing, resulting in either a 'stamp of approval' for adequately qualified projects or detailed recommendations for improvement for those projects requiring further refinement.

The appraisal process consisted of several key phases:

1. Project Preparation

- a. Projects complete technical and financial due diligence.
- b. Comprehensive pitch decks are finalised and rehearsed.
- c. The financial ask for each project is identified and validated.
- d. Capital-raising capacities are tested.
- e. Projects meeting the criteria receive a stamp of approval, signalling readiness for the contracting phase.

2. Appraisal Event Preparation

- a. Selection of the appraisal event format and location: Brussels and Barcelona.
- b. Investor identification and engagement: creating the investor panel.
- c. Appraisal event execution.

3. Post-Appraisal Proceedings

- a. Feedback from the appraisal event is reviewed and integrated into project improvement plans.
- b. Investor feedback informs necessary project reframing and further engagement strategies.
- c. Ongoing communication with investors maintains momentum and supports project progression.

This document outlines the structure and activities of this appraisal process, emphasizing its role in facilitating project readiness and engagement with investors.

DEFINITE Consortium Partners

Logo	Organisation	Type	Country
	ICLEI EURO	Small and medium-sized enterprise	Germany
	Circle Economy	Non-governmental organisation	The Netherlands
	Stad Gent	Municipality	Belgium
	Bankers without Boundaries (BwB)	Non-governmental organisation	Ireland
	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	University	Greece

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List of abbreviations used

- BM – Business Model
- BwB – Bankers without Boundaries
- CCRI – Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
- CE – Conformité Européenne
- CLN – Circular Library Network
- CSO – Coordination and Support Office
- CapEx– Capital Expenditures
- FIB – Financial and Investment Baseline
- IoT – Internet of Things
- LCA – Life Cycle Assessment
- NTUA – National Technical University of Athens
- OpEx – Operational Expenditures
- PDA – Project Development Assistance
- SAFE – Simple Agreement for Future Equity
- TIP – Technical and Impact Potential
- USP – Unique Selling Proposition
- WP – Work Package

Purpose of this document

This document outlines the investor project appraisal process and execution as carried out by the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium. It provides a detailed overview of the stages involved in preparing projects for financing, ensuring their technical and financial readiness, and aligning them with investor expectations. The process culminated in a formal appraisal event, following which projects received a 'stamp of approval' or were provided with actionable recommendations for improvement.

By describing the phases of project preparation, event execution, and post-appraisal proceedings, the document highlights the consortium's structured approach to enhancing project viability and fostering productive engagements with investors. This robust model demonstrated its strengths with respect to supporting capital-raising efforts and helping to accelerate project implementation.

1. Appraisal process structure

The appraisal preparation process was structured into three key phases, each with a series of planned steps to support overall success and ensure that the projects were robustly and effectively evaluated.

1. Project Preparation

Objective: Establish the technical and financial readiness of each project.

- **Technical and Financial Due Diligence:**
 - Assessed the viability and soundness of each project's framework.
- **Development of Pitch Decks:**
 - Created, refined, and rehearsed compelling presentations tailored for potential investors.
- **Validation of Financial Requirements:**
 - Identified and confirmed the financial needs of each project.
 - Evaluated the capacity of projects to raise the required capital.
- **Stamp of Approval Process:**
 - Issued formal approval to projects meeting established criteria, allowing them to proceed to the next stage.

2. Appraisal Event Preparation

Objective: Plan and execute the appraisal event.

- **Event Logistics:**
 - Determined the format and location of the event (e.g., events in Brussels and Barcelona).
- **Investor Engagement:**
 - Identified and onboarded a diverse and influential panel of investors.
- **Execution:**
 - Organised a platform for project presentations, feedback sessions, and networking opportunities with potential investors.

3. Post-Appraisal Proceedings

Objective: Consolidate event outcomes and advance projects toward investor engagement.

- **Feedback Integration:**
 - Reviewed insights from the event and incorporated them into updated project plans.
 - Addressed identified gaps or areas for improvement.
- **Project Adjustments:**
 - Reframed project approaches based on investor input.
- **Continuous Communication:**
 - Maintained engagement with investors to foster collaboration and support ongoing development.
- **Next Steps:**

- Positioned projects for the investor brokerage phase, expected between January and April 2024.

2. Project preparation

The following section highlights all the steps that were necessary to ensure projects were ready for the investor appraisal event, from the completion of due diligence requirements to the identification of the financing ask and the testing of capital-raising capacity, culminating suitably qualified projects receiving the 'stamp of approval' required to attend the appraisal event.

2.1 *Completion of the technical and financial due diligence*

2.1.1 **Financial Due Diligence**

The financial due diligence process undertaken by the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium was a comprehensive, iterative effort to assess the financial health, scalability, and investment readiness of four circular economy start-ups. Each project required a tailored approach to refine its financial framework, validate its business model, and align its growth strategy with investor expectations. While the process varied based on the unique challenges and maturity levels of each project, it consistently focused on creating robust financial models and actionable recommendations for improvement.

- **Tissel**

Tissel, a circularity and innovation hub supported by the Roubaix municipality in France, presented a unique case where revenue generation was limited to lease rentals and supplementary services. The financial due diligence process began with a detailed review of tenancy agreements to determine average lease rates and validate rental income assumptions. Revenue projections were mapped to anticipated area expansions and potential new services, such as a planned restaurant and events venue.

The consortium worked closely with the Tissel team to model cost structures, incorporating logistics services and utilities provision, and to account for future revenue-sharing agreements with the municipality. Capital expenditure plans, including investments in facility renovations, solar installations, and Établissements Recevant du Public compliance, were evaluated for feasibility and alignment with projected cash flows. This engagement highlighted the need for Tissel to diversify its revenue streams and manage long-term operational sustainability effectively.

Legal support: Unique aspects of the project, specifically identifying the steps and requirements needed for transitioning ownership from Ville de Roubaix to the Manufactures Tissel, required legal support. This was subcontracted to a local legal firm. This work was essential for the project's capital-raising efforts and thus to gaining the stamp of approval required to participate in the appraisal event.

- **Circular Library Network**

Circular Library Network (CLN) faced the challenge of introducing an innovative product in an evolving market. The due diligence process focused on refining its revenue model, which combined hardware sales and a software-as-a-service (SaaS) platform. Revenue assumptions were closely scrutinised, particularly the pricing and adoption rates for the Valdis and IL hardware systems.

To support the start-up's financial projections, the consortium conducted a detailed market size analysis, estimating the potential for growth across European and North American markets. Direct costs were calculated based on contract manufacturing arrangements, while operating expenses included scaling efforts such as marketing and team expansion. The capital requirements for developing the SaaS platform and expanding production capabilities were integrated into a 10-year financial model. This

collaborative effort helped CLN articulate its scaling strategy and present an investor-ready business case.

Legal support: The subcontracted legal support for CLN was twofold: (a) drafting of a simple agreement for future equity (SAFE) agreement adapted to the Icelandic context, and (b) the patent application for intellectual property registration in the US. Both these actions were instrumental to ensuring CLN would be able to raise capital from Icelandic and non-Icelandic investors for its Icelandic entity.

- **Tehdassaari**

Tehdassaari, a living lab for the circular economy, required extensive work to model its diverse revenue streams. The project had begun generating income from lease rentals and cafe operations, with plans to expand into events, accommodations, and app-based revenue. The consortium's financial due diligence began with analysing existing rental agreements and occupancy rates to validate current revenue streams.

Projections for event revenue and accommodations were informed by benchmarking studies on similar facilities, incorporating assumptions about ticket pricing, average daily rates, and seasonality. The app-based revenue model was developed with input from the start-up to assess potential monetisation avenues, including subscriptions and commission-based transactions. A key focus was aligning the project's ambitious Capital Expenditure (CapEx) plans, including renovations and material bank development, with its long-term cash flow projections.

- **Return2Sender**

Return2Sender, a start-up that aims to revolutionise pallet wrapping through reusable solutions, presented a unique challenge as it was in the pre-revenue stage. The due diligence process centred on conceptualising revenue streams and translating market size data into actionable projections. Using industry benchmarks and market trends, the consortium built a financial model that projected wrap sales and servicing revenue over 10 years.

Particular attention was given to cost structures, as the start-up initially relied on third-party ateliers for production but planned to transition to an in-house facility. CapEx requirements for the new facility, along with investment in European Movement Standards (EUMOS) compliance testing equipment, were integrated into the model. Since there was no historical data available, the financial model relied heavily on validated assumptions and sensitivity analyses to account for uncertainties in scaling and adoption rates.

Legal support: Return2Sender received subcontracted assistance for the patenting application of its proprietary technology from a Belgian legal firm.

2.1.1 Technical Due Diligence

The technical due diligence services provided by the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium focused on scaling the impact and operational capabilities of the four projects. This was delivered using a needs-based approach to provide bespoke support where it was most required. An initial in-person session was arranged with each of the projects to determine what technical services were needed and which of the partners was best placed to provide this assistance, with the option to subcontract external service providers where this was the most appropriate course of action.

- **Tissel**

Three services were developed for the Tissel project:

1. Building Decarbonisation as a service, aiming to propose a set of tailored energy efficiency interventions for the building of the hub. This service was subcontracted so that engineers could do an assessment and energy audit of the building, from the shell to the heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning systems to develop a set of interventions that can be implemented to increase the building's energy efficiency and reduce its overall carbon footprint.
2. Material Symbiosis. The hub strives to establish circular material streams in-house, to increase its overall impact. The service aims to highlight the ongoing status of material consumption by SMEs that work in the building to bring forward potential synergies and material exchange.
3. The third service includes "benchmarking," aimed at enabling Tissel to learn from and get inspired by other European circular hubs. By understanding how other hubs function and the activities they carry out, it is expected that this will inform future decision-making at Tissel and accelerate their growth and expansion through the lessons learned from more mature hubs, particularly in terms of their business models, how different hubs generate revenue, and the challenges they have overcome along the way.

- **Circular Library Network**

Three services were developed for the CLN project in Reykjavik. The first one was a comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) done for the most borrowed items of one of the sites of the CLN. The LCA will be a key cornerstone in making impact related information available to investors and ultimately to clients, improving the Unique Selling Proposition (USP) of the system. This service was subcontracted to enable a local expert to work with CLN on site.

The second one is a 'social impact assessment' which is a framework to enable the CLN project to assess the impact it has on the daily lives of people in communities that adopt the approach. The result of this service is an easy-to-use framework that the CLN project can share with its customers as a way of measuring the intangible benefits associated with the approach, as the improved health, reduced stress, and increased spare income and overall improved quality of life.

The third service includes a component of a market analysis, as the CLN project was eager to find out the potential markets it could expand to across industries and value chains. This service resulted in an analysis of potential markets that the CLN approach could expand to. The three services were complemented by a 'procurement training' aiming to enable the project to learn how to access and leverage public funding.

- **Tehdassaari:**

Four services were offered to Circular Economy Incubator Hub in Nokia. The first one was app development, including the first development of the app, and some mock-ups that could be used in the pitch to investors. This service was subcontracted to enable the hub to be in contact with local experts that could further support them after the support of DEFINITE CCRI.

The second one was a 'benchmarking' service aimed at bringing forward best practices from other hubs, which could support decision making in Nokia's hub. This service was

developed similarly to the one in Tissel with a set of interviews with other hubs across Europe.

The third one was the 'energy efficiency interventions' service. This service aims at enhancing the energy efficiency of one of the buildings of the hub and enabling its tenants to adopt energy efficient practices and behaviours.

The fourth one was the 'strategic partner analysis' where a framework was developed to enable the hub to assess that potential tenants are in line with the core values and have the same aspirations as the hub.

- **Return2Sender**

The Return2Sender project in Gent was provided with three services. The first one was an LCA to assess the impact of the reusable pallet wraps at a product level, comparing it to the most conventional, most used pallet wrapping material – stretch film, as well as an eco-version of stretch film. Results have shown the clear superiority of Return2Sender over conventional stretch film in environmental terms.

The second one was a component of a market analysis. The project was eager to learn on the one hand if potential companies were willing to switch to reusable pallet wraps, and on the other hand to figure out whether social ateliers could be potential partners. So, this service had two components, one was to prepare a tailor-made questionnaire addressed to sustainability, operations and logistics managers to gauge the feasibility of adopting reusable pallet wraps. The second component to the service was to subcontract a local expert to interview social ateliers and gauge their willingness to be part of the production of the pallet wraps

The third service was a 'technology optimization service' so that the project could figure out what is the budget required to produce a series of products, the estimated cost per unit, the number of operators needed, and the footprint of the machine. This service was subcontracted to a local engineering team, that could also work with the project after the completion of Definite CCRI's support. The three services were also complemented by a 'procurement training' aiming to enable the project to learn how to access and leverage public funding.

2.2 *Completion of pitch decks and pitch rehearsals*

Oftentimes, the pitch deck is the first interaction an investor will have with prospective business – it is an important opportunity to make a significant first impression and stand out from the crowd. On one level the pitch deck is a critical information document, detailing key information about the company, the market in which it exists, and all necessary financial and operational details. On another, it is a visual and verbal storytelling tool that allows readers to look beyond the relevant numbers and information to get a sense of what the company represents, its brand image, and the reasoning for its existing in the first place.

For circular economy businesses, when the associated innovation and potential market are often not fully appreciated by investors, it is even more important to ensure market drivers are properly reflected in the pitch deck. To portray this effectively, each of the project pitch decks followed a similar approach to ideation, with three key facets:

Problem/purpose: To properly sell the solution and the need for the business to exist, it is necessary to first 'sell' the problem - to really ensure that the audience understands and cares about the issue to be solved. During the development of the pitches great attention was placed on this, and each of the pitches designated time to explaining the social and environmental challenges that motivated their entrepreneurship.

- **Example:** The Circular Library Network recognised a bias against access-based solutions, in that some audiences do not properly recognise the impact the approaches have. By properly illustrating the dichotomy of overconsumption on one hand and financial inaccessibility of necessary appliances on the other, the unique value of the library of things infrastructure becomes much more apparent.

Traction: Investors want to see that the business is moving in the right direction, and that steps are being taken to develop and grow. Optimally this would be in relation to revenue generation and market expansion, but oftentimes start-ups are not yet at that stage of maturity. For the projects that were not yet revenue generating it was necessary to communicate traction in other areas, in these cases critical milestones were used instead, showing proactivity and an understanding of necessary steps towards going to market.

- **Example:** Tehdassaari have intentions to grow their site into a circular economy hub for innovation, events and material sharing, but before doing so it was necessary to first prove that the site could be a destination that people in the local area were willing to visit. For the project, traction numbers were not only financial, but also key milestones regarding numbers of visitations, required renovations, and demand for on-site services.

Opportunity: The opportunity presented to circular economy businesses is not just determined by the strength of the business model. In the European context especially, circular economy businesses are likely to benefit from adapting regulation and shifts in demand. It is critical that the audience is convinced that the potential market exists and is ideally growing, only then does the business represent an opportunity.

- **Example:** One of the unique value propositions of the Return2Sender pallet wrapping solution is that it is EUMOS certified and can safely transport pallets to the EU standard. However, the solution is further benefitted by upcoming regulation, the EU Plastic and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), which will require 40% of all transport packaging to be reusable by 2030.

Each of the four projects had different starting points in regard to pitching their ideas - the key aim was to find a style and approach that fit with the image and ethos of the business, and to develop a presentation that portrayed this succinctly and coherently. Each of the project owners attended a mock pitching presentation workshop facilitated by DEFINITE-CCRI to ensure adequate preparation for the appraisal event proper.

2.3 Identification of the financial ask for each project

Determining the financial ask was a critical component of the due diligence process for each project.

The financial ask represents the capital required by the start-up to meet its operational, developmental, and scaling objectives while ensuring alignment with investor expectations. For all four projects, this process involved analysing projected cash flows, assessing CAPEX requirements, and aligning funding needs with strategic milestones.

- **Tissel**

Tissel's financial ask was centered on supporting its transition from a rental-income-dependent model to a diversified revenue base. Key components of the funding requirement included:

- **CAPEX Investments:** Renovations to existing facilities, construction of a restaurant and bar, and installation of solar panels to enhance sustainability.
- **Operational Buffer:** Bridging cash flow gaps during the development phase of new revenue streams, such as events and utilities services.
- **ERP Compliance Costs:** Funding to ensure adherence to French ERP standards for public safety and accessibility.

The funding ask was structured to cover immediate infrastructure investments and create a reserve for operational and marketing costs required to attract tenants and visitors.

- **Circular Library Network**

For CLN, the financial ask was designed to enable the production and scaling of its innovative self-checkout systems while expanding its SaaS platform. Key considerations included:

- **Production Scaling:** Establishing manufacturing capacity for the IL hardware model, which would enter the market in 2026.
- **Market Expansion:** Funding targeted marketing efforts to penetrate new markets in Europe and North America.
- **Technology Development:** Enhancing the SaaS platform to improve customer experience and drive subscription revenue.

The financial ask accounted for significant upfront costs associated with entering new markets, establishing partnerships, and scaling operations, while maintaining flexibility to adjust based on market demand.

- **Tehdassaari**

Tehdassaari's financial ask was aligned with its vision of becoming a leading hub for circular economy innovation and community engagement. The primary drivers of its funding requirements were:

- **Facility Renovations:** Upgrading existing buildings to accommodate tenants, events, and cultural activities.
- **Event Infrastructure:** Developing spaces for workshops, concerts, and private events to generate supplementary revenue.
- **Material Bank Development:** Creating a central repository for reusable materials to support circular economy practices.
- **Technology Integration:** Building an app-based resource-sharing platform to enhance user engagement and drive monetization.

The financial ask was structured to support both immediate operational needs and long-term investments in infrastructure and technology.

- **Return2Sender**

For Return2Sender, the financial ask focused on transitioning from a prototype to a fully operational business. The funding requirements were shaped by:

- **Production Facility:** Establishing an in-house manufacturing facility by 2027 to reduce reliance on third-party ateliers and achieve cost efficiencies.
- **Working Capital:** Funding the production of reusable pallet wraps to meet initial demand and build inventory.

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- Market Penetration: Supporting market entry efforts in Belgium, France, and the Netherlands, including pilot programs with large clients.
- EUMOS Compliance Equipment: Acquiring testing machinery to streamline regulatory compliance and reduce recurring costs.

Given its pre-revenue stage, the financial ask for Return2Sender emphasized securing smart capital to establish a production base, validate its business model, and prepare for scaling.

Key Considerations Across All Projects

The identification of financial asks followed a common methodology, ensuring clarity and alignment with each project's growth trajectory:

1. Linking Capital to Milestones

Each funding request was directly tied to critical developmental and operational milestones, such as:

- a. **Product Launches:** Funds allocated to cover research, development, marketing, and distribution efforts.
- b. **Market Expansions:** Capital earmarked for scaling operations into new regions or demographics, addressing regulatory requirements, and adapting to local market demands.
- c. **Infrastructure Upgrades:** Investments to enhance operational capacity, improve technology stacks, or streamline production facilities. By aligning capital needs with these milestones, the projects demonstrated how funding would drive measurable progress, thereby building investor confidence.

2. Incorporating

Contingencies

To mitigate risks and account for potential delays or unforeseen challenges, a contingency buffer was included in every financial ask. This approach provided:

- a. **Flexibility:** Ensuring that projects remained agile and responsive to unexpected cost overruns or disruptions.
- b. **Resilience:** Safeguarding against uncertainties without compromising the overall timeline or deliverables. This foresight underscored the projects' preparedness and reduced the likelihood of needing emergency funding, which could disrupt strategic plans.

3. Balancing

Equity

and

Debt

Recommendations on the funding mix were tailored to each project's stage, asset base, and long-term financial goals. Key considerations included:

- a. **Minimizing Dilution:** For early-stage projects, equity was carefully allocated to preserve founder control and maintain valuation integrity.
- b. **Leveraging Debt:** In later stages, with established cash flows or tangible assets, debt financing was encouraged as a cost-effective way to meet capital needs without sacrificing equity.
- c. **Optimizing Sustainability:** The mix of equity and debt ensured that projects could scale effectively while maintaining a healthy balance sheet and avoiding financial strain.

2.4 Testing of capital raising capacity

The capacity of the four start-ups to raise capital was a critical aspect of the due diligence process. This involved evaluating their financial models, market positioning, and investment readiness, as well as assessing their appeal to various investor categories. The DEFINITE-CCRI consortium undertook a

structured approach to test each project's ability to secure funding by engaging potential investors, simulating investor pitches, and analyzing feedback from these interactions.

Approach to Testing Capital Raising Capacity:

- **Evaluation of Investor Appeal**
Each project was assessed for its attractiveness to different types of investors, including venture capitalists, angel investors, and institutional financiers. This evaluation focused on:
 - Market Potential: The scale of the addressable market and the start-up's competitive positioning.
 - Scalability: The ability of the business model to expand operations while maintaining profitability.
 - Impact Alignment: The alignment of the start-up's mission with the growing investor focus on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria.
- **Pitch Simulations and Refinement**
The consortium facilitated mock pitch sessions to simulate real investor interactions. These sessions allowed the start-ups to test their narratives, refine their pitches, and prepare for common investor questions. Feedback was provided on the clarity of the value proposition, strength of the financial case, and overall presentation. Specific focus was placed on communicating the scalability of revenue streams, risk mitigation strategies, and the alignment of funding requests with projected milestones.
- **Market Engagement**
The consortium conducted targeted outreach to investors operating in relevant sectors, including circular economy, sustainability, and innovation. For instance, Tissel's potential appeal lay in impact-driven real estate investors, while Return2Sender attracted interest from early-stage VCs focused on green logistics solutions. Conversations with these investors provided insights into their priorities, including preferred financing structures and expectations for returns.
- **Analysis of Feedback**
Feedback from investors was analyzed to identify common themes and areas requiring improvement. Key observations included:
 - Investors prioritized clear pathways to profitability, particularly for pre-revenue start-ups like Return2Sender.
 - Technical readiness, such as achieving certifications or patents, played a significant role in building investor confidence.

Capital Raising Readiness for Each Project

- **Tissel (Roubaix)**
Tissel demonstrated strong appeal to investors interested in community-driven, impact-focused projects. Its reliance on municipal support and plans for diversifying revenue streams were seen as strengths, but investors emphasized the need for detailed plans to achieve financial independence from municipal funding over time.
- **Circular Library Network (Reykjavik)**

CLN's innovative product offering and SaaS model were well-received, especially by impact-focused VCs. However, its relatively nascent revenue streams and the need to scale manufacturing capabilities were identified as areas requiring additional focus.

- **Tehdassaari (Nokia)**

Tehdassaari's positioning as a circular economy hub with potential for diversified revenue streams made it attractive to a set of Finnish investors, including those in sustainable real estate and innovation. Investors highlighted the importance of delivering on CAPEX plans and ensuring operational scalability.

- **Return2Sender (Ghent)**

As a pre-revenue start-up, Return2Sender's focus was on validating its business model and demonstrating market traction through pilot projects. While its potential to address regulatory and environmental needs resonated with investors, the lack of historical performance data presented a challenge.

2.5 Stamp of approval issuance

Once all the necessary due diligence steps had been completed, the financial ask had been identified and the capacity to raise capital within a timeline which aligned with the DEFINITE-CCRI timeline, the whole consortium deliberated on the decision to move all four projects having received technical assistance to the project appraisal phase.

Therefore, on October 31, 2024, all projects received the following email, awarding them with a "stamp of approval" justifying the decision and outlining the next steps.

Object: Stamp of approval and participation to the Appraisal Event

*Congratulations on your successful progress in the due diligence phase and on receiving your **stamp of approval** to attend the in-person appraisal event on November 13, 2024.*

Since the start of the financial and technical assistance phase of DEFINITE CCRI, you have completed all necessary steps and actively participated in workshops and deep dive meetings to refine your projects.

Notably:

*For the **financial** due diligence, you have:*

- *Supported the completion of financial models for projected costs and revenues, firm valuation, and required capital.*
- *Provided inputs and content for the pitch decks to be used during the appraisal event.*
- *Reviewed existing risks, their materiality, and mitigation strategies.*
- *Shared your strategic and financial-related vision and priorities.*
- *Compiled the requested financial and legal documents for investors.*
- *Completed the required work for the successful execution of the subcontracted legal due diligence.*

For the **technical** due diligence, you have:

- *Provided the necessary input to increase your technical, environmental and social impact as well as to bring forward the circularity of your approach.*
- *Collaborated with the technical partners and shared your particular needs to advance your project.*
- *Co-created where necessary the approach to solve complex issues for the project (e.g., measuring the social impact or the impact for the local community).*

*In recognition of your diligent efforts, we are pleased to award you the **stamp of approval to advance to the appraisal phase** and begin reviewing capital-raising options based on your needs and investor interests. The DEFINITE CCRI team will continue to provide ongoing support to ensure fundraising expectations are met and investor due diligence requests are addressed. We look forward to your pitching sessions and the upcoming period dedicated to fulfilling your fundraising goals.*

3. Appraisal event preparation

3.1 Selection of the appraisal event format and location: Brussels and Barcelona

The objective of the appraisal events in Brussels and Barcelona was twofold:

- a. To test the venture's ability to pitch in front of professional investors and collect their feedback on assumptions, financials and investment decisions
- b. To kickstart the investor engagement process, aiming to receive the support by one or multiple investors taking part in the panel

The choice of where to hold the appraisal event was informed by a few criteria:

- Full completion of all the necessary due diligence deliverables
- Avoidance of competing events
- Proximity to project key locations
- Availability of project managers
- Proximity to relevant investors
- Synergies with existing events
- Cost considerations

After the assessment of several options, such as joining forces with the Smart City Expo of Barcelona and the CCRI 3rd annual workshop, the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium decided to split the appraisal event into two separate events:

3.1.1 Barcelona Appraisal Event – Selection rationale

Due to the unavailability of the Circular Library Network founder during mid-November and the carrying out of the Norrsken Impact Week in Barcelona during the first week of November, the consortium decided to hold the event at a partner organisations' facilities on November 7th.

The consortium planned on taking advantage of the numerous impact investors interested in early-stage circularity ventures, which could have joined the appraisal event being held only 15 minutes away from the Impact Week facilities. During the same days, furthermore, the Smart City Expo was also taking place, further increasing the chances of attracting investors at the event or networking with investors at the Expo right after the event had taken place.

The decision on the facilities where to host the event fell on BAX, an innovation company and consultancy operating, among other topics, in the circularity and sustainable development fields. This came at no cost to DEFINITE-CCRI which benefitted from the connection with BAX that BwB and the Circular Library Network had already established.

3.1.2 Brussels Appraisal Event – Selection rationale

The decision to hold the key appraisal event in Brussels, hosted by the 3rd CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop, was motivated by several factors:

- The opportunity to join forces and identify synergies with other CCRI PDA initiatives
- The proximity to project facilities in Roubaix, Nokia and Ghent
- The proximity to relevant investors
- The lower costs for travel and facility reservation

The appraisal event in Brussels took place on November 13th.

3.2 *Investor identification and engagement: creating the investor panel*

When selecting the investor panel, the DEFINITE-CCRI team relied on existing signatories of the Expression of interest letters, selected investors by project leads and potentially interested capital providers based on their portfolio and investment rationale.

This shortlisting led to the creation to two different types of investor panels, as outlined below

3.2.1 Barcelona Appraisal Event – Investor selection

When it comes to the selection of investors for the Barcelona event, the DEFINITE CCRI team reached out to investors bilaterally and made the event public for investors to attend. The following professionals attended the event:

Entity #1: Green Accelerator

Company representative: Anastasia Zhdanovich

Investor type: Accelerator and early-stage investor

Headquarters: Ibiza, Spain

Entity #2: LCIC

Company representative: Leo Riviera

Investor type: Early-stage impact investor

Headquarters: London, UK

Entity #3: Mission Control Lab

Company representative: Jessica Cobb

Investor type: Early-stage impact investor

Headquarters: Amsterdam, the Netherlands

Entity #4: Untap!

Company representative: Erik Afzelius

Investor type: Circular start-up

Headquarters: Stockholm, Sweden

Entity #5: TeamLabs Barcelona

Company representative: Carla Filannino

Investor type: Circular Incubator

3.2.2 Brussels Appraisal Event – Investor selection

The Brussels investor panel was made up by three entities represented by four professionals:

Entity #1: Trividend

Company representative: Pieter-Jan Van der Velde

Investor type: early-stage impact investor

Ticket size: €250k - €1M

Headquarters: Ghent, Belgium

Reasons for the selection:

- Early on engagement with the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium through existing contacts in the Ghent Municipality
- Previous knowledge about Return2Sender
- Geographical expertise in the Flanders region and previous expertise in circularity

Entity #2: Polestar Capital

Company representative: Pieter-Jan Van der Velde

Investor type: Impact and Circularity Investor

Headquarters: Amsterdam, the Netherlands

Reasons for the selection:

- Polestar has a significant track record investing in circularity, renewable energies and impact at large
- Geographical expertise in the Benelux area

Entity #3: Business Tampere

Company representatives: Karoliina Tuukkanen, Pirkko Eteläaho

Investor type: Business accelerator and capital raising facilitator

Headquarters: Tampere, Finland

Reasons for the selection:

- Previous knowledge about the Tehdassaari project
- Strong link with the capital providing entity, Business Finland
- Expertise regarding operations put forward by Tehdassaari including the Material Bank
- Regional expertise

3.3 *Appraisal event execution*

3.3.1 **Barcelona Appraisal Event – The Barcelona Circular Innovation Summit**

Date: November 7th, 2024

Location: BAX, Carrer de Casp, 118, 120, L'Eixample, 08013 Barcelona, Spagna

Session link: <https://lu.ma/y8j8bo5t>

Organized with the objective of garnering attention and ensuring the presence of impact investors joining the Norrskan Impact Week in Barcelona. It was centered around the presentation of the Circular Library Network and its achievements after the first round of due diligence.

The DEFINITE CCRI team therefore created an event, named the Barcelona Circular Innovation Summit, to highlight the technology and innovation component of the event, and arranged the meeting in the BAX facilities. Appendix 1 reports the banner used to advertise the event as well as some pictures relating to this Appraisal Event.

The agenda was structured as follows:

- 10:00 – 10:30 **Attendees reception**
- 10:30 – 11:00 **Presentation of the BAX activities**
- 11:00 – 11:30 **DEFINITE CCRI presentation**
- 11:30 – 12:00 **Circular Library Network presentation**
- 12:00 – 13:00 **Round table discussion**

Key takeaways

- 1) The format of the event, with multiple speakers and 10 total attendees, allowed for a dynamic exchange and was keenly appreciated by those who joined. It permitted a dynamic set of exchanges and deep interactions
- 2) Attendees provided extremely insightful feedback to the CLN value proposition and operations, which was noted and incorporated into the deck
- 3) CLN remained in touch with all attendees and organised follow up conversations with all of them

3.3.2 **Brussels Appraisal Event - 3rd Coordination and Support Workshop**

Date: November 13th, 2024

Location: CDMA - European Commission, Rue du Champ de Mars, Ixelles, Belgium

Session link: <https://ecorys.idloom.events/ccri-3rd-workshop>

Organising the appraisal event for three out of four projects in Brussels was strategic under multiple points of view. First, it was perfectly located close to project main locations and investors. Second, the organisation of the CCRI CSO 3rd coordination and support workshop would allow to identify synergies

with other CCRI PDA projects as well as to showcase the work to EU Commission representatives and other partnering organisations. Third, partnering with the CCRI CSO for the event organisation allowed for a reduction in costs.

The agenda was structured as follows:

- 09:00 – 11:00 **Opening remarks by organizers and financial considerations by BwB**
11:00 – 12:00 **Pitch by Tehdassaari, Nokia**
12:00 – 13:00 **Pitch by Return2Sender, Ghent**
- 14:00 – 15:00 **Pitch by Tissel, Roubaix**
14:00 – 16:30 **Workshop on Construction and Circular Buildings – Tehdassaari participation**
16:30 – 18:00 **Closing ceremony with roundtable and PDA takeaways – Tissel participation**

Key takeaways:

- 1) Investors provided a positive review of the setup of the event and expressed interest in having more details about the key revenue streams and the strategies for revenue generation. More detailed information can be found in paragraph 4.1 of this document
- 2) The workshop on construction and circular buildings allowed Tehdassaari to explore the revenue streams related to the creation of a material bank
- 3) During the closing ceremony, Tissel highlighted the key role of CCRI, and DEFINITE-CCRI in particular, in examining the revenue streams and legal setup of the venture for fundraising purposes, as well as the key impact metrics resulting from the operations of the facilities

4. Post-appraisal proceedings

4.1 *Post-event project feedback review*

The appraisal events, both in Barcelona and in Brussels, provided valuable insights into enhancing investment readiness and overall project strategies. A recurring theme in the feedback was the importance of clear and targeted communication. Participants were encouraged to refine their pitches to focus on key revenue drivers, financial projections, and long-term sustainability benefits. Tailoring presentations to specific audiences, such as impact investors, hospitality companies, or retail managers, was highlighted as a critical step toward capturing stakeholder interest effectively. Establishing a compelling narrative that connects vision, impact goals, and revenue strategies was deemed essential.

The need for simplification and focus emerged strongly throughout the feedback. Complex business models and broad scopes were seen as barriers to scalability and investor confidence. Streamlining operations and narrowing focus on fewer, more impactful revenue streams were recommended as ways to improve transparency and appeal. Additionally, providing clear breakdowns of investment allocation and aligning financial plans with projected outcomes were identified as crucial elements for building trust with investors.

Sustainability and impact metrics were highlighted as key drivers for attracting investment. Participants were advised to present measurable indicators of their contributions to circular economy principles, decarbonization, and social benefits. Even preliminary or estimated KPIs were considered valuable for demonstrating commitment to achieving tangible outcomes. Aligning these metrics with regulatory drivers, such as EU legislation, was noted as an effective way to strengthen market potential.

Lastly, the feedback underscored the importance of addressing market readiness and scalability challenges. Strategies for balancing ongoing development with market entry, accelerating revenue generation, and navigating cost barriers were discussed. Participants were encouraged to develop clear frameworks for stakeholder engagement and explore ecosystem-based approaches to manage diverse investment needs across project components. Overall, the event emphasized the significance of clarity, focus, and impact-driven strategies in securing long-term success.

4.2 *Post-event investor feedback integration*

The DEFINITE CCRI team spent a month supporting the project teams in integrating the feedback from the appraisal event into their pitch decks. The process began with detailed review sessions where the teams and the CCRI team analyzed the feedback to identify key areas for improvement, such as clarifying revenue strategies, simplifying business models, and highlighting sustainability impacts.

Using an iterative approach, the teams reworked their pitch narratives to connect their vision, financial goals, and impact strategies effectively. The DEFINITE CCRI team provided continuous feedback on multiple draft versions, ensuring the pitches were polished and targeted to specific audiences.

4.3 *Post-event investor engagement*

The DEFINITE CCRI team took the initiative to contact all the investors who participated in the appraisal event. Through these engagements, the team worked to consolidate and expand on the feedback

received, ensuring a deeper understanding of the investors' perspectives and priorities. These discussions provided an opportunity to clarify any outstanding points, address specific concerns, and gather additional insights that could further strengthen the projects.

Building on this feedback, the DEFINITE CCRI team collaborated with the investors to outline clear next steps aimed at positioning the projects for successful capital raising. This included aligning expectations on financial strategies, impact metrics, and project milestones. By fostering open communication and maintaining strong relationships with the investors, the team ensured that the projects remained aligned with market needs and investment criteria, preparing for future funding opportunities.

5. Key takeaways and learnings

The report highlights a deeply collaborative and iterative process aimed at preparing four circular economy start-ups for investment. Through comprehensive technical and financial due diligence, the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium worked to bridge gaps in financial literacy, operational readiness, and investment appeal, setting these projects on a path toward scalable and sustainable growth.

- **Tailored Approaches are Essential**

Each start-up presented unique challenges and opportunities, reflecting the diversity within the circular economy space. From Tissel's dependence on municipal support to Return2Sender's pre-revenue stage, the process emphasized the importance of tailoring due diligence efforts to the specific needs, maturity levels, and business models of each project.

Learning: *Start-ups require customized appraisal frameworks to address their unique circumstances, ensuring relevance and practical application.*

- **Foundational Financial Literacy is a Gap**

A recurring theme across all four projects was the lack of deep financial understanding among founders. Many required significant support to conceptualize revenue streams, refine cost structures, and align CAPEX plans with strategic objectives.

Learning: *Building financial literacy among founders is critical for developing robust financial models and fostering investor confidence. Educational interventions and hands-on guidance can significantly enhance a start-up's investment readiness.*

- **Collaboration is Key**

The iterative nature of the process—marked by constant engagement, feedback loops, and refinements—demonstrated the power of collaboration. Founders worked closely with the consortium to align assumptions, refine projections, and develop compelling narratives for their pitches.

Learning: *Close collaboration between start-ups and external advisors accelerates readiness and ensures alignment with investor expectations.*

- **Early Market Validation Increases Investor Confidence**

Start-ups like CLN, which could demonstrate early traction through tenant agreements or pilot sales, were better positioned to attract investor interest. Conversely, projects in the conceptual or pre-revenue stages, like Return2Sender, faced greater scrutiny.

Learning: *Demonstrating early market validation, even in small pilot programs, significantly strengthens a project's appeal to investors.*

- **Clear and Transparent Communication Builds Trust**

Investors valued start-ups that were transparent about their challenges, risks, and assumptions. Proactively addressing gaps in market analysis or operational scalability helped establish credibility and trust.

Learning: *Open and transparent communication, coupled with clear mitigation strategies for identified risks, fosters stronger investor relationships.*

- **Capital Raising is a Journey, Not a Transaction**

The process highlighted that securing investment is not merely about presenting financial models or pitches but about aligning long-term visions with the right investors. For all projects,

the focus was on building lasting relationships and preparing for sustained engagement beyond the initial funding round.

Learning: *Start-ups should approach capital raising as an ongoing process, emphasizing strategic alignment and long-term partnerships over immediate funding needs.*

- **Circular Economy Start-ups Face Unique Challenges**

The circular economy start-ups in this appraisal demonstrated the dual challenge of operating in niche, emerging sectors while addressing complex regulatory and environmental requirements. These factors often made projections more uncertain and required additional investor education about the sector's dynamics and potential.

Learning: *Circular economy start-ups benefit from tailored support that addresses their unique challenges, including navigating regulations, demonstrating impact, and building investor awareness about the sector.*

Appendix

Appendix 1 *Barcelona Circular Innovation Summit Banner and Pictures*

Barcelona Circular Innovation Summit

10:00 – 12:00
November 7th, 2024

Key Partners

Circular Library Network's Anna De Matos pitching to investors and attendees

Appendix 2 *Brussels Appraisal Event Pictures*

Tehdassaari's Fuad and Perttu pitching to investors in Brussels

Return2Sender's Johan and Adriaan pitching to investors in Brussels

BWB's Tommaso Buso speaks about the financing and funding landscape for circularity in Europe

BwB's Tommaso Buso sits on a panel to assess pitches from circular companies

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